

QC Report - Agilent Technologies : 2 Color Gene Expression

QCMetrics InRange (8 of 11)

Date	Wednesday, August 11, 2010 - 12:07	BG Method	No Background
Image	US83403541_251897210115_S01 [1_2]	Background Detrend	On(FeatNCRRange, LoPass)
Protocol	GE2_105_Dec08 (Read Only)	Multiplicative Detrend	True
User Name	melblab	Dye Norm	Linear Lowess
Grid	US83403541_251897210115_S01_grid (from grid_file)	Linear DyeNorm Factor	0.274(Red)0.561(Green)
FE Version	10.5.1.1	Additive Error	5(Red)7(Green)

Sample(red/green)

Spot Finding of the Four Corners of the Array

Evaluate Grid

Feature	Local Background	
	Red	Green

	Red	Green	Red	Green
Non Uniform	10	11	19	17
Population	111	119	1229	294

Spatial Distribution of All Outliers on the Array

532 rows x 85 columns

FeatureNonUnif (Red or Green) = 13(0.03%)

GeneNonUnif (Red or Green) = 7 (0.022 %)

- BG NonUniform ● BG Population
- Red FeaturePopulation ● Red Feature NonUniform
- Green FeaturePopulation ● Green Feature NonUniform

Net Signal Statistics

Agilent SpikeIns:

	Red	Green
# Saturated Features	0	0
99% of Sig. Distrib.	618	626
50% of Sig. Distrib.	482	449
1% of Sig. Distrib.	292	298

Non-Control probes:

	Red	Green
# Saturated Features	0	0
99% of Sig. Distrib.	94416	33739
50% of Sig. Distrib.	583	473
1% of Sig. Distrib.	249	241

Red and Green Background Corrected Signals (Non-Control Inliers)

Features (NonCtrl) with BGSubSignals < 0: 16977 (Red); 18866 (Green)

Negative Control Stats

	Red	Green
Average Net Signals	442.83	422.34
StdDev Net Signals	11.05	7.43
Average BG Sub Signal	1.09	1.14
StdDev BG Sub Signal	10.86	7.55

Local Bkg (inliers)

	Red	Green
Number	43791	44726
Avg	55.22	25.99
SD	2.46	1.50

Foreground Surface Fit

	Red	Green
RMS_Fit	3.52	4.54
RMS_Resid	17.21	12.61
Avg_Fit	448.18	427.96

Reproducibility: %CV for Replicated Probes

Median %CV Signal (inliers)		Agilent SpikeIns	
Non-Control probes		Red	Green
Red	Green	Red	Green

BGSubSignal	11.79	12.59	-1.00	-1.00
ProcessedSignal	3.91	4.49	-1.00	-1.00

Array Uniformity: LogRatios

	Non-Control	Agilent SpikeIns
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AbsAvgLogRatio	0.10	0.24
AverageS/N	7.30	3.59

Sensitivity:Agilent SpikeIns - Ratio of Signal to Background for 2 dimmest probes

(+)E1A_r60_n11		(+)E1A_r60_a97	
(g)	(r)	(g)	(r)
0.9	1.0	1.1	1.0

Spatial Distribution of Significantly Up-Regulated and Down-Regulated Features

#Up-Regulated:1350 (Red) ; #Down-Regulated:1160 (Green)

▲ Up-Regulated □ Down-Regulated

LogRatio Versus Log Processed Signal

- Significantly down regulated
- Significantly up regulated
- Used to normalize
- Not differentially expressed

Agilent SpikeIns Signal Statistics

Probe Name	Exp	Obs	SD	S/N
(+)E1A_r60_n9	-1.00	-0.18	0.06	3.14
(+)E1A_r60_a107	-0.48	***	***	***
(+)E1A_r60_a135	-0.48	-0.52	0.06	8.06
(+)E1A_r60_n11	-0.48	-0.09	0.18	0.48
(+)E1A_r60_1	0.00	-0.01	0.08	0.18
(+)E1A_r60_a20	0.00	-0.02	0.11	0.18
(+)E1A_r60_3	0.48	-0.51	0.20	2.58
(+)E1A_r60_a104	0.48	-0.44	0.03	13.17
(+)E1A_r60_a97	0.48	0.13	0.10	1.23
(+)E1A_r60_a22	1.00	-0.29	0.09	3.26

Evaluation Metrics for GE2_QCMT_Dec08

Metric Name	Value	UpLim	LowLim	IsMandatory
AnyColorPrcntFeatNonUnif...	0.03	1.00	NA	False
absE1aObsVsExpCorr	0.01	NA	0.86	False
absE1aObsVsExpSlope	0.04	NA	0.85	False
gE1aMedCVBkSubSignal	-1.00	25.00	NA	False
gNegCtrlAveBGSubSig	1.14	10.00	-20.00	False
gNegCtrlSDevBGSubSig	7.55	15.00	NA	False
gNonCntrlMedCVBkSubSignal	12.59	25.00	NA	False
rE1aMedCVBkSubSignal	-1.00	25.00	NA	False
rNegCtrlAveBGSubSig	1.09	4.00	-20.00	False
rNegCtrlSDevBGSubSig	10.86	6.00	NA	False
rNonCntrlMedCVBkSubSignal	11.79	25.00	NA	False

◆ In Normal Range ◆ Evaluate

Agilent SpikeIns: % CV of Average BG Sub Signal

Agilent SpikeIns: Expected LogRatio Vs Observed LogRatio

